

Form for the knowledge level after the refactoring work on Code Smells and Collaboration in OSS projects

This form aims to gather information from students of the Quality and Software Maintenance classes about the knowledge acquired by students after the refactoring work on Code Smells and Collaboration in OSS projects.

** Indica uma pergunta obrigatória*

1. E-mail *

Term of Informed Consent

This is an invitation for you to answer the questionnaire:

"LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE ABOUT CODE SMELLS".

Attention

This survey will not evaluate your answers as right or wrong, and it is anonymous and for academic purposes only.

Disclosure

This survey will be anonymized, and the data will be used for scientific publication.

2. **After reading the Informed Consent Form: ***

Marcar apenas uma oval.

I Agree

I do not wish to participate

Personal Information

3. **What is your name? (We will need this information to compare before and after the class work) ***

4. **What is your gender? ***

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Male

Female

Other

I do not wish to say

5. **What is your major? ***

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Digital Design

Computer Engineering

Software Engineering

Computer Networks

Computer Science

Information Systems

6. What is your period? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- 1º
- 2º
- 3º
- 4º
- 5º
- 6º
- 7º
- 8º
- 9º
- 10º
- Outro: _____

7. What is your class? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Software Quality
- Software Maintenance
- Both

Information about Code Smells and Software Refactoring**8. What is your perception of the level of knowledge you acquired in the work on Code Smells? ***

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Minimum
- Basic
- Intermediate
- Advanced
- Expert

9. Which code smells did you refactor the most in the work? (Refer to the definitions of code smells: <https://refactoring.guru/refactoring/smells>) *

Marque todas que se aplicam.

- God class
- Duplicated Code
- Long Parameter List
- Large Class
- Long Method
- Data Class
- Large Component
- Too Many Props
- Inheritance Instead of Composition
- Props in Initial State
- Direct DOM Manipulation
- Force Update
- JSX outside the render method
- Uncontrolled Components
- Large File
- Any Type
- Many Non-Null Assertions
- Missing Union Type Abstraction
- Enum Implicit Values
- Multiple Booleans for State
- Props with Children Pitfall
- Outro: _____

10. Which code smells did you find most challenging to refactor? *

Marque todas que se aplicam.

- God class
- Duplicated Code
- Long Parameter List
- Large Class
- Long Method
- Data Class
- Large Component
- Too Many Props
- Inheritance Instead of Composition
- Props in Initial State
- Direct DOM Manipulation
- Force Update
- JSX outside the render method
- Uncontrolled Components
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- Any Type
- Many Non-Null Assertions
- Missing Union Type Abstraction
- Enum Implicit Values
- Multiple Booleans for State
- Props with Children Pitfall
- Outro: _____

11. What were the main challenges you encountered in the practice of refactoring code smells? *

12. What benefits did you identify in the practice of refactoring code smells? *

13. What soft skills and hard skills do you think you acquired through the execution of the work? Examples: *
(<https://www.codemotion.com/magazine/it-careers/trending-hard-skills-and-soft-skills-in-software-development/>)

Collaboration in Open Source Software Projects

14. What level of collaboration did you perform in the project you refactored? *

Marque todas que se aplicam.

- I implemented new features
- I resolved minor issues
- I resolved major issues
- I performed code refactoring
- Outro: _____

15. Was the selected project active and with recent collaborations? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Yes
- Não

16. How many open issues did the selected project have? *

17. How many issues did you open and resolve in the project? *

18. How many submitted issues were accepted? *

19. What is your perception of the difficulty level of collaboration in the selected project? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Very Easy
- Easy
- Moderate
- Hard
- Very Hard

20. What difficulties did you encounter in submitting and resolving a code quality issue in the selected project? *

21. What is your perception of the benefits of collaboration on an open-source software project in terms of improving code quality? *

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Google Formulários

